

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe
with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Moldova: An Introduction

Viorel Girbu, *Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova, NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Moldova has developed framework legislation that guides the regulation of the local authority's competencies in accordance with the principles specified in the European Charter of Local Self-Government. Article 1 of the Law on Administrative Decentralization in Moldova guarantees that local public authorities have the right and the effective capacity to regulate and manage, according to the law, an important part of public affairs under their own responsibility and in the interest of the local population. In this regard, the process of administrative decentralization is guided by the principles of subsidiarity, equity among local authorities, correspondence of resources with competences, financial solidarity, institutional dialogue, partnership, and responsibility of local authorities.

The current process of developing the regulatory framework tends to build a system of attributions/transfers of competencies between central administration and local authorities, characterized by functionality, clarity, stability, correlation with available resources and administrative capacity of the local public authorities (LPAs). The aim is to provide public services in an unrestricted (improved access), efficient (as low costs as possible) and effective manner (according to the needs and requirements of beneficiaries, including vulnerable groups), ensuring a minimum level of service quality.

As a rule, decentralized competencies, such as those relating to urban planning and management, maintenance of educational institutions and activities in the cultural and social protection domains, management of the municipal enterprises, and passenger car transport, are those responsibilities that are transferred to LPAs, to provide public services according to the specific local needs and preferences of the beneficiaries. In this situation, LPAs should enjoy autonomy in the management and provision of these competencies – central public authorities should no longer use direct management and decision tools, but only indirect tools such as the development of specific public policies, mandatory quality standards, the provision of incentives and penalties (especially financial), monitoring, control, law enforcement and evaluation.

In reality, however, the implementation of the principles contained in the Law on Administrative Decentralization is not straightforward. Many, if not all the problems in this respect stem from the historical inheritance of a very fragmented system of LPAs at the communal level, a fragmentation which has been compounded by high levels of both emigration and internal migration. This has left many communes extremely small and with limited resources and capacities. Indeed, despite a symmetric decentralization model, many rural local governments are not able to provide many of the services they are responsible for,

according to the nomenclature of local responsibilities. Notably, the provision of services related to the collection and management of household waste, including sanitation and maintenance of landfills; water supply distribution, construction and maintenance of sewerage and wastewater treatment systems; construction, maintenance and lighting of local public streets and roads; local public transport is mostly lacking in the vast majority of rural LPAs and only partially available in the urban-type LPAs in Moldova. 'This situation is mainly due to limited progress in the area of financial decentralization and overall limited level of the financial resources managed by the LPAs. In 2018 over 54 per cent of the state budget revenues in Moldova were destined for transfers to other components of the National Public Budget (BPN). Local budgets are highly dependent on transfers from the state budget, with over 70 per cent of local budget revenues in 2017-2018 coming from these transfers.'¹

Though all of the public services and competences of the LPAs are part of the same list approved by law, the actual degree of local decision-making autonomy differs for each competence. A major criterion that influences the level of the competences exercised by LPAs is the source of funding for the service delivery. As a result, and particularly with respect to social sector functions, most public services are managed hierarchically and are still very centralized according to the secondary legislation. A recent assessment on the progress of decentralization in Moldova points on the fact that '[a]lthough the reform of local public finances started in 2013 aimed at implementing a mechanism for forming local budgets that would increase the degree of financial autonomy of local public authorities, in the period after the reform there was an opposite trend.'²

In the social domain the education sector is achieving best performance from the perspective of service access. The access to education has a relative uniform coverage throughout the territory of the country. This is possible because of the significant financial support provided from the central budget in form of categorical grants and high involvement of the central authorities in the overall management of the sector. However, the situation limits the degree of control by LPAs over the service provision that is in reality a deconcentrated service rather than decentralized competence of the LPAs.

¹ Dumitru Budianschi, 'Autonomia financiară în Republica Moldova: evoluția veniturilor bugetelor locale' (Expert-Grup 2019) <https://www.expert-grup.org/media/k2/attachments/Autonomia_financiara_in_Republica_Moldova.pdf>.

² Expert-Grup, 'Reforma descentralizării - spre centralizare: în perioada anilor 2016 – 2018 dependența autorităților locale de transferurile de la bugetul de stat a sporit, iar autonomia financiară s-a diminuat' (*Expert-Grup*, 26 June 2019) <<https://www.expert-grup.org/ro/activitate/comunicate-de-presa/item/1824-reforma-descentralizarii-spre-centralizare-in-perioada-anilor-2016-2018-dependenta-autoritatilor-locale-de>>.

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Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization

Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration

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Budianschi D, 'Autonomia financiară în Republica Moldova: evoluția veniturilor bugetelor locale' (Expert-Grup 2019) <https://www.expert-grup.org/media/k2/attachments/Autonomia_financiara_in_Republica_Moldova.pdf>

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